

High performing solid-state organic electrochemical transistors enabled by glycolated polythiophene and ion-gel electrolyte with a wide operation temperature range from -50 to 110 °C

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Abstract

The development of organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs) capable of maintaining their high amplification, fast transient speed, and operational stability in harsh environments will advance the growth of next-generation wearable & biological electronics. In this work, we successfully demonstrated a high performance solid-state OECT (SSOECT), showing a recorded high transconductance of 220 ± 59 S/cm, ultrafast device speed of ~ 10 kHz with excellent operational stability over 10000 switching cycles and thermally stable under a wide temperature range from -50 to 110 °C. The developed SSOECTs were successfully used to detect low-amplitude physiological signals, showing a high signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) of 32.5 ± 2.1 dB. For the first time, the amplifying power of these SSOECTs was also retained and reliably shown to collect high-quality electrophysiological signals even under harsh temperatures (-50°C and 110°C). The demonstration of high-performing SSOECTs and its application in harsh environment are core steps toward their implementation in next-generation wearable electronics & bioelectronics.

1. Introduction

Organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs) featured with high amplification, low operating voltage and excellent biocompatibility have been envisioned as the basic building blocks for next-generation wearable electronics and bioelectronics.^[1–5] However, the conventionally used aqueous electrolytes cause undesirable issues such as leakage, challenging the long-term stability of the devices and generating variable device performance depending on storage or operating conditions (e.g., humidity, temperature, and presence of oxidants).^[4,6,7] There are also stability issues related to passive swelling of the channel as well as complicated ion transport associated with hydration in the presence of water molecules in aqueous electrolyte.^[7,8] In addition, OECTs capable of functioning in high- or low-temperature environments are of great interest for many microelectronics applications such as decoders in digital circuits and voltage amplifier for electrophysiological monitoring,^[3,9–11] but the aqueous electrolytes limit the broader use of OECTs in these applications. For instance, the temperature required for currently commercially packaged electronic devices can reach ~90 °C. Additionally, the development of OECTs capable of functioning over a wide operating temperature range will further advance their applications, such as in polar expedition and space exploration. To overcome these constraints, the integration of soft solid electrolytes in OECTs (solid-state OECTs; **Figure 1a**) with efficient ionic gating is highly desirable.

Despite the recent progress in developing SSOECTs, ion penetration is typically slower in a solid electrolyte than in a liquid media; hence high-performing SSOECT showing both high transconductance and fast switching response is still lacking (Table S1).^[4,5,9,12–18] Studies about the thermal stability of SSOECTs are also rare, especially on the device performance below room temperature or higher temperatures above 90 °C.^[11,19,20] To date, the solid electrolytes employed are mainly limited to polyelectrolytes such as poly(sodium-4-styrene sulfonate) and ion-conducting polymers blended with salt.^[12,17,20,21] While these polymer electrolytes have shown promising characteristics, they still have limitations in operational and thermal stability, where their moisture content varies with time and environmental conditions, thus affecting their ionic conductivity and consequently device performance. One promising polymer electrolyte reported so far is using the high chain dipole moment of poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-co-HFP) copolymer mixed with electrochemically stable ionic liquids to form an elastomeric ionic gel, which exhibits great flexibility and ion migration efficiency.^[14,22] The non-volatilizable nature of PVDF-co-HFP/ionic liquid system ensures stable operation of various electronics, including neuromorphic computing and resistive

random-access memory systems, and has been shown to be temperature resilient up to 90 °C.^[11] In addition, the most widely used channel material for SSOECTs is poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene):poly(styrenesulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS).^[5,9,14,23–25] So far, the highest normalized transconductance reported for PEDOT:PSS-based SSOECT is 210 S/cm with a transient speed of ~140 Hz.^[5] However, a film of PEDOT:PSS is especially complex due to its heterogeneous nature consisting of the blend of two ionomers and has been reported to exhibit microstructure changes at different temperatures.^[26,27] Currently, the operating temperature window for PEDOT:PSS-based SSOECTs is limited between -30 – 20 °C.^[19,20] Over the last few years, the incorporation of glycolated side chains in the conjugated backbone has been pursued to develop mixed ionic-electronic semiconducting polymers, where the glycolated side chains allow efficient ion transport and the conjugated backbone enables charge transport. Among the various library of homogeneous polymers, the current benchmark is poly[3,3'-bis(2-methoxyethoxy)-2,2'-bithiophene]-co-[3,3'-bis(2-(2-(2-(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)ethoxy)-2,2'-bithiophene], p(g1T2-g5T2), which not only possesses a high normalized transconductance of ~156 S/cm, but also exhibits excellent operational stability retaining 98% of its initial current after ~700 doping/dedoping cycles operated in aqueous electrolyte.^[7] However, its use in SSOECT and study of its thermal stability has not been explored yet.

Here, we successfully demonstrated a high-performing SSOECT using the p(g1T2-g5T2) as the active channel material and a solid electrolyte consisting of poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-co-HFP) and 1-Ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (EMIM BF₄). A record high normalized transconductance (220 ± 59 S/cm), fast transient response (~10 kHz) as well as good electrochemical doping/de-doping stability over 10⁴ switching cycles was attained in this SSOECT. The developed p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECTs were successfully used to detect and amplify low-amplitude electrocardiography (ECG) signals, showing a high signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) of 32.5 ± 2.1 dB, indicating high-quality signals, which was attributed to the ultrafast speed and high normalized transconductance of the SSOECTs. In addition, the SSOECTs were capable to operate under a wide temperature range from -50 to 110 °C without degradation in their transconductance values, thus broadening their operating temperature limits, and their switching speed was found to increase at increasing temperatures. For the first time, the amplifying power of these SSOECTs was also retained and reliably shown to collect high-quality ECG signals even under harsh temperatures (-50 °C and 110 °C).

2. Results

Solid-state organic electrochemical transistors. Figure 1a presents the device architecture of our solid-state OECT (SSOECT). The SSOECT was composed of an active material with thiophene backbone functionalised with glycolated side chains (p(g1T2-g5T2)), a solid electrolyte consisting of a poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-co-HFP) ionic conductive polymer and a hydrophilic ionic liquid of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate (EMIM BF₄) (**Figure 1b**). The high chain dipole moment of the PVDF-co-HFP copolymer interacts with the EMIM BF₄ to form an elastomeric ionic gel that allows for facile ion migration under an applied electric field, in which the doping anion of BF₄ ion has been found to be effective in doping glycolated conjugated polymers.^[28,29] Transfer characteristics and the associated transconductance of the p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECTs doped with BF₄ anion are presented in **Figure 1c-d** and **Figure S1a**. Specifically, upon application of a negative gate bias (V_G), anions from the electrolyte are injected into the channel to dope the p(g1T2-g5T2), inducing the accumulation of holes and hence the increase of drain current (I_D). Typical pinch-off behaviors were observed in the corresponding output characteristic (**Figure S1b**). The negligible hysteresis observed in both transfer and output curves indicates efficient ion penetration and transport in the bulk channel. The steady-state device characteristics of the SSOECT can be evaluated using the transconductance (g_m), which is the derivative of the transfer curve ($g_m = \partial I_D / \partial V_G$). This SSOECT exhibits significantly high normalized transconductance of 220 ± 59 S/cm (normalized by channel dimension dW/L , where the d , W , and L are the channel thickness, width, and length, respectively) and a high drain current ON/OFF ratio of $\sim 10^5$. Its high steady-state performance is mainly attributed to the hydrophilic ethylene glycol chains in p(g1T2-g5T2), which enables sufficient penetration and transport of ions in the bulk channel for electrochemical doping.^[7] It is worth noting that this is the highest normalized g_m value among all reported SSOECTs devices (Table S1),^[4,5,9,12-18] showing the great potential of amplifying small input signals for various sensing applications. Meanwhile, at the saturation regime, the g_m value can be defined using $g_m = \frac{dW}{L} \mu C^* (V_T - V_G)$, where μ is the device mobility, C^* is the volumetric capacitance and V_T is the threshold voltage. Of which, the product of μC^* can be used to reflect the steady-state ionic/electronic properties of the active material. As detailed in Table S2, the extracted μC^* value was 426 ± 73 F cm⁻¹ V⁻¹ s⁻¹, demonstrating the excellent mixed ionic-electronic transport properties of the p(g1T2-g5T2) polymer and sufficient ion mobility in PVDF-co-HFP polymer electrolyte for efficient doping and dedoping of the channel.

The transient measurements for p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECTs further revealed that it could be switched on in $108 \pm 9 \mu\text{s}$ (~ 10 kHz) when doped with BF_4 anions (**Figure 1e**). It is also surprising that this SSOECT (using Au-PEDOT:PSS as gate electrode) showed ~ 2 times faster transient speed than a device with operated in 0.1 M NaCl electrolyte (using Ag/AgCl pellet as gate electrode; **Figure 1e**). As previously reported, the degree of hydration of the dopant ions in the electrolyte can affect both the transient response speed of the device and the reversibility of the electrochemical doping process.^[8] To understand the influence of degree of hydration in the dopant anions on the device transient speed, we characterized and compared p(g1T2-g5T2)-based OECTs gated in two different aqueous, ionic liquid and solid electrolytes. Comparable transient speed was observed for the devices operated in aqueous electrolytes (0.1 M NaCl; $197 \mu\text{s}$ and 0.1 M EMIM BF_4 ; $270 \mu\text{s}$), in agreement with previous report.^[28] In contrast, the device gated with pure EMIM BF_4 ionic liquid electrolyte showed similar transient speed as the device with PVDF-co-HFP/EMIM BF_4 solid electrolyte, and a factor of ~ 2 faster than the device gated in 0.1 M NaCl aqueous electrolyte. We therefore postulate that the observed fast transient speed of SSOECT was mainly attributed to the reduced degree of hydration in the dopant anions in solid electrolyte. According to the Bernards model, the transient response time of an OECT channel current to a gate voltage step is the RC time constant of the ionic circuit between the gate and channel, $\tau_i = R_S C_{CH}$, where R_S is the electrolyte resistance and C_{CH} is the channel capacitance,^[30] we therefore employed electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) to evaluate the corresponding R_S values in 0.1 M NaCl electrolyte and PVDF-co-HFP/EMIM BF_4 electrolyte (**Figure S2**). The lower R_S values seen in the solid electrolyte as compared to 0.1 M NaCl electrolyte further validates our observations. Compared with state-of-the-art SSOECTs, our p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECT exhibits ultra-fast transient response while simultaneously exhibiting highly normalized transconductance (**Table S1** and **Figure 1f**).

Additionally, benefiting from the high electrochemical stability of p(g1T2-g5T2) polymer and the non-volatilizable nature of the electrolyte, as shown in **Figure 1g**, the p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECT exhibits superior operational stability over long operation hours with no significant drop of its initial doping current after 10,000 cycles of pulse measurement. As previously reported, the redistribution of glycolated side chain on the conjugated backbone led to less active swelling (10%) of the polymer during electrochemical doping process, thus enabling superior pulse stability.^[7] In this work, the incorporation of solid-state electrolyte further minimized both the passive and active swelling of the channel, therefore ensuring great

cyclic operation stability in this p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECT. We further evaluated the shelf-life of this p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECTs, via measured both the steady-state and transient-state performance of the device over time/each day (Figure S3). It was observed that the devices could be reliably operated for 7 days, with a loss of ~ 10% in g_m , but no obviously change in its transient speed within 1 week.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of solid-state organic electrochemical transistors (SSOECTs). (b) Molecular structure of the active materials of p(g1T2-g5T2) and the used solid electrolyte of PVDF-co-HFP electrolyte with ionic liquid of EMIM BF₄. (c) Transfer characteristics and (d) the associated transconductance, and (e) drain current transient speed (with V_G varies from 0 to a voltage of peak g_m occurred, at $V_D = -0.6$ V) of p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECTs when gated in two aqueous electrolytes (using Ag/AgCl pellet the gate electrode), pure ionic liquid (using Ag/AgCl pellet the gate electrode), and solid electrolyte (using Au-PEDOT:PSS as gate electrode), with a channel dimension of $W/L=100 \mu\text{m}/10 \mu\text{m}$ and thickness $d= \sim 28$ nm. (f) Benchmarking of previously reported SSOECTs and SSOECTs developed herein by comparing

their corresponding steady- and transient-state performance. Note that the channel dimension is critical role to the device's performance. To obtain a fair comparison among the reported works on SSOECTs, the transconductance was normalized by its channel dimension (dW/L), and the transient speed was normalized by $d\sqrt{WL}$. (g) Pulse stability of the p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECTs with the V_G varies from 0 to a gate voltage at which the peak g_m occurs and operated under ambient conditions.

Since the hydrophobic-hydrophilic properties of the anions in the electrolyte can affect ion penetration and transport in the bulk channel,^[28,29,31] we further investigated another anion type, namely bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)amide (TFSI), while employing the same EMIM cation (**Figure S4a-b**). Device performance varied upon anion substitution, with significantly higher normalized transconductances and faster device speeds observed when p(g1T2-g5T2) was doped with hydrophilic anions (BF_4) compared to the one doped with hydrophobic TFSI anions (**Figure S4c-e** and **Table S2**). To further examine the critical role of hydrophilic-hydrophobic properties of anions on the transport in the bulk channel and thus the device performance, the other widely used conjugated polymer of P3HT with hydrophobic side chain was characterized (**Figure S4a**). As presented in **Figure S4f**, both TFSI and BF_4 anions can effectively dope the P3HT devices and present good steady-state device performance, in terms of high normalized peak g_m value of 86 ± 23 and 104 ± 34 S/cm and good μC^* value of 262 ± 60 and 309 ± 91 F $\text{cm}^{-1} \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ for TFSI and BF_4 doped channels, respectively (**Table S2** and **Figure S4g**), while simultaneously exhibiting excellent current ON/OFF ratio of $\sim 10^5$ (**Table S2**). However, a much lower V_T of -0.36 ± 0.01 V and relatively small hysteresis were seen in the P3HT channel doped with hydrophobic TFSI than the channel doped with hydrophilic BF_4 anions (-0.72 ± 0.03 V) (**Figure S4f**). The increased hysteresis implies poorer ion transport of BF_4 in the P3HT bulk channel, which further underlines the importance of the hydrophilic-hydrophobic nature of anions in the electrochemical doping efficiency. Interestingly, owing to the difference in hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity of the side chains in p(g1T2-g5T2) and P3HT polymers, the transient behavior is found to vastly differ when doped with BF_4 and TFSI anions. For p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECTs, the BF_4 -doped device is faster than the TFSI-doped device (0.108 ms versus 0.298 ms; **Figure S4e**). In contrast, the TFSI-doped P3HT devices exhibited faster speed than BF_4 -doped devices (460 ms versus 1620 ms; **Figure S4f**). This finding underscores the importance of selecting specific anions to maximise the performance of different active materials in OECTs.

SSOECTs for Electrophysiology Monitoring. The use of electrocardiography (ECG) to record cardiac activity can provide useful information to distinguish the normal function or abnormalities among patients with palpitations, dizziness, shortness of breath, chest pain, or an irregular heartbeat. However, some abnormal cardiac rhythms like cardiac fibrillation are usually weak and easily masked or distorted by noises and, therefore require a high signal-to-noise ratio for discrimination and diagnosis.^[32] The advantages of SSOECT such as high transconductance, fast response speed, and low operating voltage, allow monitoring ECG signals even at a very low level of input potential, serving as a local amplifier of electrophysiological signals. As previously mentioned, the SSOECTs based on BF₄-doped p(g1T2-g5T2) and TFSI-doped P3HT possessed similar g_m but vastly different transient speeds (Supporting information, **Figure S5**). We thus compared the ECG recordings from the skin using these two devices as the electrophysiological transducer. In the configuration for ECG measurement (**Figure 2a**), one commercial gel electrode was adhered to the volunteer's chest and connected to the gate electrode of the SSOECT, while another electrode was adhered to the left forearm and connected to the source electrode of SSOECT, serving as a ground for measurement. The ECG signals were recorded at different gate biases, while a constant drain bias of -0.6 V was applied to record the channel current (I_D) of SSOECTs. The potential generated by cardiac activity was transmitted to the current signal through the SSOECT. As shown in **Figure 2b** and **Figure S6**, ECG signals acquired by p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECT revealed a typical waveform morphology featuring a well distinguished P-wave, T-wave, and QRS complex, corresponding to the expected electrical activity of the human heart, giving rise to high-quality ECG signals.^[33] In addition, the time-frequency spectrogram (0-26 Hz) of ECG pulse was obtained by Fast Fourier transformation (FFT) (below image in **Figure 2b**). The frequency identification of typical ECG peaks is clearly distinguishable along with the signal magnitude, which is crucial to diagnosing cardiac abnormalities in clinical healthcare.^[32] However, in the case of P3HT SSOECT, significant fluctuations in ECG traces were recorded, rendering peak recognition challenging, hence leading to an unreliable ECG signal. The time-frequency spectrogram revealed a lower frequency identification of less than 5 Hz for P3HT SSOECT, which correlates well with its observed slower transient response. Therefore, the significant noise comes from the slow transient speed upon inputting a gate potential, which can disrupt a wide range of signal transformations. In addition, ECG recording at zero gate bias is also demonstrated for p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECT, with high-quality and long-term continuous signals collection and without noticeable peak fluctuations and baseline drift over time (**Figure 2c**).

The applied gate bias can also modulate the amplified amplitude of ECG signal. As shown in **Figure 2d**, **Figure S6**, and **Figure S6**, different gate bias from -0.3 V to 0.3 V was applied on p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECT (-0.3V to -0.8V for P3HT SSOECT) and channel current was recorded to investigate the peak-to-peak (R-S) amplitude of ECG signals. The tuneable peak-to-peak amplitude results from the conductivity modulation behaviors through the applied gate bias of the SSOECT. For example, the peak-to-peak amplitude measured using p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECT is around $\sim 22.3 \mu\text{A}$ at a gate bias of -0.3 V, which is much higher than that of P3HT SSOECT ($\sim 8.2 \mu\text{A}$ at a gate bias of -0.8 V). **Figure 2e** indicated the corresponding R-S peak-to-peak amplitude of the ECG signal at different operating bias in both cases, in which p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECT displayed much better modulation and less fluctuation in ECG recording. To further compare the signal fluctuation, the signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) in ECG signals for both cases was evaluated by the root-mean-squared (RMS) analysis. **Figure 2f** showed that the SNR for p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECT is around $32.5 \pm 2.1 \text{ dB}$, indicating a high-quality ECG signal. A much lower SNR ($\sim 9.2 \pm 3.6 \text{ dB}$) is obtained for P3HT SSOECT, indicating a poor ECG signal acquisition due to its slow response time. Notably, the obtained SNR value using p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECT is comparable to previously reported ultrathin OECTs (24 dB) and internal ion-gated OECTs (53.86 dB, the current benchmark)^[2,24], mainly benefited from its ultrafast device speed. Meanwhile, the high normalized g_m value guarantees a high peak-to-peak amplitude and makes it possible to detect weak abnormal cardiac rhythms. Overall, the ultrafast response and high normalized g_m in p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECT is well suited to acquire high-quality electrophysiological signals along with the potential to record other electrophysiological signals such as electromyography and electroencephalogram.

Figure 2. Electrocardiography (ECG) monitoring using p(g1T2-g5T2)- and P3HT-based SSOECTs. (a) Schematic illustration of the ECG monitoring. Commercial gel electrodes were used to acquire the electrocardiography signals. (b) ECG signals were acquired by p(g1T2-g5T2)- (left) and P3HT- (right) based SSOECTs, respectively. Below figures are the time-frequency spectrogram of ECG pulses recorded using two types of SSOECTs. (c) Long-term continuous monitoring of ECG using p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECT for one minute. (d) Comparison of ECG pulses recorded using p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECT at different gate biases (0.3 V to -0.3V from top to bottom, respectively). (e) The Peak-to-Peak (R/S) signal difference of ECG signal was recorded using p(g1T2-g5T2)- and P3HT-based SSOECTs, which were modulated by gate bias. (f) The SNR comparison of two types of SSOECTs during ECG recording.

Thermal effects on device performance. We next evaluated the effect of temperature dependence on the ionic-electronic conduction properties of our SSOECTs by performing its steady-state and transient state characteristics at various temperatures. **Figure 3a** presents the changes in transfer curves and the associated peak g_m value when operated at low temperatures ranging from 25 °C to -50 °C. As the operation temperature (T) is lowered, the doped drain

current and peak g_m value were slightly reduced, with negligible changes in V_T (**Figure 3b**). The slight decrease in drain current most probably attributed to the reduced ionic conductivity of both the electrolyte and active material at low temperature. The observed increasing hysteresis in the associated output curves (**Figure 3c and Figure S8**) as the operational temperature decreases indicates the progressively slower ions transport into/out the bulk channel. Below $T = -50$ °C, the ion-induced electrochemical doping behavior disappeared with no clear drain current modulation under the gate bias (**Figure 3a**). At the same time, its transient speed was dramatically affected by the operational temperature (**Figure 3d and Figure S9**), exhibiting a fast transient speed of ~ 0.1 ms at room temperature ($T = 25$ °C) and became ~ 16 times slower (~ 1.9 ms, that is ~ 500 Hz) at $T = -40$ °C. Its transient response dramatically increased to 17 ms at $T = -50$ °C (**Figure 3d**). The slower transient speed at low temperature can be understood by the decrease in ionic conductivity and ion mobility of the polymer electrolyte. It was worth noting that even at a low temperature of -40 °C, the p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECTs show excellent operational stability, with negligible changes in doping current after 10000 cycles of pulse measurement (**Figure 3e**), and its electrochemical doping behaviors (including doping current and transient speed) recovered once the temperature goes back to room temperature (**Figure 3f**).

Figure 3. Effect of temperature on the device performance. (a) Transfer characteristics and the associated transconductance of BF₄ doped p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECTs at different temperature range from 25 to -50 °C, (b) output curves of the p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECTs operated at 25 and -50 °C, and (c) the corresponding peak g_m value and V_T as function of the operating temperature. The channel dimension is channel width/length = 10 μm /10 μm , thickness $d = 96$ nm. (d) Transient speed of the p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECTs as a function of working temperature. (e) Pulse stability of the p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECTs operated at -40 °C. (f) Transfer characteristics of the BF₄-doped p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECTs before and after the cooling measurement.

Additionally, the p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECT shows remarkable temperature resilience at higher temperatures up to 110 °C (**Figure 4a**). The peak g_m value slightly increased when the operational temperature rose from 30 to 110 °C with a negative V_T shift (**Figure 4b**). Negligible

hysteresis was observed in all the output characteristics (**Figure S10**), indicating efficient ion transport. The device still showed excellent operational stability after 10000 cycles of pulse measurement at high $T = 110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (**Figure S11** and **Figure 4c**). At $T=120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, its maximum doping current (I_D) and peak g_m values gradually decrease with repeated electrochemical doping cycles (**Figure S12**). Interestingly, its transient speed became faster along with increasing T values (from 30 to $110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, **Figure 4d**). This enhancement can be understood by the fact that the ions are activated and thus their transport efficiency is increased at higher temperatures.^[34] We next employed grazing-incidence wide-angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS) to explore the effect of temperature on the molecular packing changes of p(g1T2-g5T2) (**Figure S13**). The pristine polymer showed predominant edge-on stacking, having a broad scattering observed around $q_{xy} = 1.55\text{ \AA}^{-1}$ (d-spacing = 4.05 \AA) and a strong lamellar peak $q_z = 0.68\text{ \AA}^{-1}$ (d-spacing = 9.24 \AA). As the polymer film is subjected to higher temperatures ($T = 50$ to $110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), no obvious change in the molecular packing (including crystallinity and π - π stacking) was observed. The thermal stability of PVDF-co-HFP/EMIM BF_4 electrolyte was also evaluated using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) (**Figure S14**). This solid electrolyte exhibits good thermal stability even at $110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ without significant weight loss. The observed progressive weight loss between 25 and $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ was mainly attributed to water uptake by the EMIM BF_4 . These results corroborate well with the superior device performance and high thermal stability of both channel and electrolyte materials for operation in a high-temperature environment.

Figure 4. (a) Transfer characteristics and the associated transconductance of BF_4 doped p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECTs at different temperature range from 30 to $110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and (b) the

corresponding peak g_m value and V_T as a function of the operating temperature. The channel dimension is channel width/length = 10 μm /10 μm , thickness $d = 96$ nm. (c) Pulse stability of the p(g1T2-g5T2) SSOECTs operated at 110 $^\circ\text{C}$. (d) Transient speed of the p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECTs as a function of working temperature.

Continuous ECG measurements of outdoor health monitoring devices at extreme environments, can provide safety precautions for assessing risk and alerting for preventive action. For examples, the extravehicular activity for spaceman, where temperature may range from -100 to 100 $^\circ\text{C}$, or the polar science and exploration, where the temperature can be very low. We therefore evaluated our SSOECTs to collect ECG signals in both low and high-temperature environments. For the ECG measurement, the wiring configuration is the same as in Figure 2a, however, the SSOECT device was placed and measured within the sealed LinKam platform system, allowing for real-time and precise control of the operating temperature. The corresponding transfer and output characteristics were presented in **Figure S15**. Notably, at low temperatures (-40 $^\circ\text{C}$ and -50 $^\circ\text{C}$), our device maintained the ability to collect high-quality electrophysiological signals, with well distinguished P-wave, T-wave, and QRS complex, having a peak-to-peak amplitude of 10.6 ± 0.1 μA and SNR of 25.6 ± 0.4 dB at -50 $^\circ\text{C}$ (**Figure 5a and 5c-d**). To the best of our knowledge, this is currently the lowest operating temperature (-50 $^\circ\text{C}$) at which SSOECTs exhibit excellent device performance, presenting the great potential of using SSOECTs for human health monitoring in harsh environments (i.e., arctic expedition). At higher temperature of 110 $^\circ\text{C}$, our SSOECTs are also robust, showing a peak-to-peak amplitude of 18.2 ± 0.7 μA and SNR of 31.0 ± 0.3 dB (**Figure 5b-d**). It is worth noting that the SNR values obtained at low- and high-temperatures are comparable to the one measured at room temperature (**Figure 5d**), indicating that our SSOECTs have the ability to collect high-quality electrophysiological signals at a wide operational temperature range (from -50 $^\circ\text{C}$ and 110 $^\circ\text{C}$).

Figure 5. ECG signals were acquired by p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECTs at (a) extremely low temperatures (0°C to -55°C) and (b) high temperatures (up to 110°C). (c) The Peak-to-Peak (R/S) signal difference of ECG signals was recorded using p(g1T2-g5T2)-based SSOECTs, which were monitored at different working temperatures. (d) The SNR comparison was picked by two types of SSOECTs during ECG recording at different working temperatures.

3. Conclusion

In summary, we successfully demonstrated a high-performing p(g1T2-g5T2)/PVDF-co-HFP-based SSOECT, with high transconductance ($220 \pm 59 \text{ S/cm}$), fast transient response ($\sim 10 \text{ kHz}$), and excellent electrochemical doping/de-doping stability over 10^4 switching cycles. The developed SSOECTs successfully detected low-amplitude physiological signals, showing a signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) of $32.5 \pm 2.1 \text{ dB}$. We further investigated the influence of operating temperature on the device performance of SSOECTs. The developed SSOECTs were capable to be operated under a wide temperature range from -50 to 110°C , without sacrificing their steady-state performance. The amplifying power of these SSOECTs can also be retained under extremely low and high temperatures, thus presenting the excellent potential of SSOECTs in more demanding applications.

4. Experimental Section/Methods

Materials and Methods: The ethylene glycolate functionalized conjugated polymer of p(g1T2-g5T2) was synthesized based on previous report.^[7] 1-Ethyl-3-methylimidazolium – tetrafluoroborate (EMIM BF₄), 1-Ethyl-3-methylimidazolium bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (EMIM TFSI), sodium chloride (NaCl), (3-glycidyoxypropyl) trimethoxysilane (GOPS), poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-hexafluoropropylene) (PVDF-co-HFP), poly(3-hexylthiophene-2,5-diyl) (P3HT) and the processing solvents were all obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. The dichloro-p-cyclophane (DPX-C) was purchased from Specialty Coating Systems, Inc. The p-Si/SiO₂ (300 nm) wafer was provided by Maideli Advanced Material Co., LTD. The PEDOT:PSS (Clevios PH1000) was purchased from Heraeus.

OECTs fabrications: OECTs were prepared using the Parylene C peel-off method as previously reported.^[4,35] Briefly, the p-Si/SiO₂ (300 nm) substrates were cleaned by soapy water, DI water, acetone, and ethanol with sonication for 10 min each sequentially. Source/drain electrodes (Cr/Au: 5 nm /50 nm) were obtained by photolithographically patterning onto the precleaned substrates by e-beam evaporation. A 2 μm thick layer of Parylene C was deposited along with an adhesion promoter of 3-(trimethoxysilyl)propyl methacrylate (A-174 Silane) using SCS Labcoater to insulate the contacts from the electrolyte. A dilute detergent solution (Micro-90, 10% by weight in deionized water) was then spun onto the Parylene C layer as an anti-adhesion layer to facilitate the subsequent peeling process. After that, a second Parylene-C layer (~2.5 μm) was deposited, which served as a sacrificial layer. The substrates were then coated with a 12 μm thick AZ P4620 photoresist, soft-baked at 110°C for 180 s, exposed with SUSS MJB4 mask aligner, and developed with AZ developer. The patterned channel area and contact pads were etched by reactive ion etching (Oxford Plasmalab80) at 50 sccm O₂, 10 sccm CHF₃, 160 W operating conditions. p(g1T2-g5T2) and P3HT solutions were prepared as followed: the polymers were first dissolved in chloroform (1 – 5 mg/mL); and stirred for 3 h at 50 °C in a glove box. The solutions were spin-coated on top of the patterned area to form the channels without further treatment. After that, the second sacrificial Parylene-C layer was peeled off. The fabricated devices were transferred inside a vacuum dry box for 24 h to fully remove the solvent entirely. To prepare the solid electrolyte, the copolymer PVDF-co-HFP was dissolved in acetone (at a weight ratio of 1:7) and vigorous stirring at room temperature for 12 h, followed by adding the ionic liquid into the solution at a weight ratio of 1:2, and vigorous vibration for 30 min. The prepared solution was then spin-coated on the fabricated OECTs at 2000 rpm for

30 s at N₂-filled GB, to form the solid electrolyte. To characterize the OEET devices, a polyimide film coated with Cr/Au/PEDOT:PSS (5 nm/50 nm/100 nm) was used as the gate electrode. To prepare the gate electrode, as received PEDOT:PSS aqueous solution was first filtered through 0.45 μm PVDF filters and then mixed with 1 wt% GOPS, vigorously stirred for 15 min. The prepared solution was spin-coated onto the Cr/Au coated polyimide film, followed by annealing at 140 °C for 1h. The Au-PEDOT:PSS gate area was 1 cm × 2 cm, indicative of more than 10⁴ times higher gate capacitance than channel capacitance for efficient gating and hence attaining the maximum electrochemical doping of the semiconductor. Unless otherwise specified, all the SSOECTs were characterized with PEDOT:PSS-based gate electrode. All the devices were characterized at ambient conditions (~25 °C, ~67% RH) unless otherwise specified.

Electrical characterization: The I-V characteristics of the films, and all the OEET device characteristics including output and transfer curves and pulse measurement, were carried out under ambient conditions using Keysight precision source/measure unit (B2912A). The threshold voltage and μC* product of all OEETs were extracted from a fit of the linear portion of the $\sqrt{I_D}$ vs V_G curves.

Electrocardiogram (ECG) monitoring: ECG was measured by placing one adhesive 3M dot electrodes (Red Dot™, Model 2239) to volunteer's chest and connected to the Au-PEDOT:PSS gate electrode of the SSOECT, while the other 3M dot electrode was adhered to the right forearm with the end connected to a voltage supply (Agilent B1500). The developed high-performing SSOECT was used as an analog current preamplifier for recording the ECG signals. The SNR is calculated as: $SNR_{dB} = 20 \log_{10}(A_{signal}/A_{noise})$, where A_{signal} is the RMS of the ECG signals and A_{noise} is the RMS of the noise collected at zero input potential (ST segment in ECG signal). The ECG measurements were taken in compliance with Institutional Review Board (Approval number: IRB-2021-144), with the consent from all the participants.

Temperature-dependent measurement: The temperature-dependent measurement of the SSOECTs was conducted using the Linkam Temperature Control Stage System (HFS600E PB4-H). The fabricated SSOECTs were measured inside a sealed chamber filled with N₂ gas. At each temperature point, the device was allowed to stabilize for 5 min before starting the measurements. To assess the effect of temperature on the ability of the SSOECTs to amplify the ECG signals, commercially available 3M gel electrodes (Red Dot™, Model 2239) were used to attach to the human body and wired to the SSOECT device, while this SSOECT device

was placed and measured within the sealed LinKam platform system, which enables real-time and precise control of the operating temperature.

Materials Characterization: Grazing incidence wide-angle X-ray diffraction (GIWAXS) was performed on the Nanoinxider (Xenocs) to explore the molecular packing of p(g1T2-g5T2) films heated at different temperatures. Thermogravimetric Analysis was performed on DTG-60H, operated in an nitrogen environment, and slowly heated from room temperature to 800 °C at a rate of 5 °C/min. The thickness of the polymer films was characterized by Alpha-Step profilometer (KLA-Tencor). Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) were carried out to evaluate the electrolyte resistance (R_s) when operated in 0.1M NaCl electrolyte, pure EMIM BF₄, and PVDF-co-HFP/EMIM BF₄ electrolyte, using Metrohm Autolab potentiostat. In order to be as close as possible to the operation condition of device characteristics, for the EIS measurement, a comparable OECT channel was shorted and used as working electrode, while the reference and counter electrodes were shorted and connected to the corresponding gate electrode (AgAgCl pellet (Warner Instruments) for 0.1 M NaCl electrolyte and pure EMIM BF₄, and Au-PEDOT:PSS electrode for PVDF-co-HFP/EMIM BF₄ solid electrolyte). EIS was performed over a frequency range from 10⁵ Hz and 10 Hz, with a 10 mV single sinusoidal signal without DC offset bias. The obtained impedance data was fit to an equivalent circuit of $R_s(R_p||C)$, where R_s is the electrolyte resistance, R_p is the charge transfer resistance, and C is the channel capacitance.

Statistical Analysis: Data presented were representative of at least 3 independent experiments, and quantitative results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) unless otherwise specified.

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